

Interaction of Sulphuryl Chloride with Substances containing the Reactive Methylene Group. Part II.

By K. G. NAIK AND N. T. TALATI.

The present communication is a continuation of the work done by Naik and Shah (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 11).

The main results of the interaction of sulphuryl chloride with various amides and substituted amides of malonic and methyl malonic acids, obtained herein, can be summarised as under:—

I. (a) Conversion of the group $:\text{CH}_2$ into $:\text{CCl}_2$ or (b) of the group $:\text{CHMe}$ into $:\text{CClMe}$ by complete replacement of the methylene hydrogen atom or atoms by chlorine, without chlorination of the nucleus:—Malon-di-*m*-nitranilide, malon-di-*p*-nitranilide, malon-di-*o*-nitranilide, malon-diethylamide, malon-di-isobutylamide, malon-diheptylamide, malon-di-1:4:5-xylidide, and malonamide undergo this change under (a) whereas methylmalon-diethylamide, methylmalon-di-isobutylamide, and methylmalon-dibenzylamide undergo this change under (b).

Further it was found that the same type of reactivity persisted even among the aliphatic amides of the methylmalonic acid. It may be noted here that in these compounds, one of the hydrogen atoms of the methylene group is replaced by the methyl group. Thus methylmalon-diethylamide, on interaction with sulphuryl chloride, yields a monochloro-derivative:—

II. Conversion of the group $:\text{CH}_2$ into $:\text{CHCl}$ without chlorination of the nucleus:—Malon-tetraphenylamide undergoes this change.

Type I. Malon-di-*m*-nitranilide reacts with sulphuryl chloride as under:—

The fact that the substance produced from malon-di-*m*-nitranilide has this constitution, is based on arguments similar to those advanced by Naik and Shah (*loc. cit.*).

It may, however, be pointed out that malontetraphenylamide, where there is no hydrogen atom attached to the nitrogen, yields a

monochloro-derivative. These go to prove that sulphuryl chloride reacts at the methylene group.

Type II. The interaction of malontetraphenylamide with sulphuryl chloride as stated above follows a different course, yielding a monochloro-compound:—

In this case, in spite of the two hydrogen atoms of the methylene group being available, only one is attacked. This course of the reaction is not an abnormal one, as is evident from the work of Naik (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 381), Naik and Shah (*loc. cit.*) and West (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2196).

The experiments described here afford clear evidence, with regard to the reactivity towards sulphuryl chloride of compounds containing the reactive methylene group, that it depends on the electronegative character of the adjoining groups. For example, sulphuryl chloride reacts more vigorously with malon-dinitranilide than with malonamide, while the reaction with ethyl malonate is the most vigorous, taking place at the ordinary temperature. So in a series like:—

- (I) $\text{CH}_2(\text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}_2)_2$
- (II) $\text{CH}_2(\text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{NO}_2)_2$
- (III) $\text{CH}_2(\text{CO}_2\text{Et})_2$

the reactivity which is less pronounced in (I) becomes more and more manifest with increasing negative character of the adjoining groups.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Malon-di-m- and -p-nitranilides.—These amides were prepared by condensing ethyl malonate and the corresponding nitraniline in equimolecular proportions, on the basis of the preparation of malonamide by Whiteley (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 36). The solid obtained was extracted with alcohol and finally crystallised from acetic acid in granulated mass. The *m*-compound had m. p. 196°, whereas the *p*-compound—a faintly yellowish crystalline one—had m. p. 243°.

Preparation of Malon-di-o-nitranilide.—The reaction with ethyl malonate and *o*-nitraniline did not go even at 200°. Hence the amide was prepared from malonic acid and *o*-nitraniline using phosphorus oxychloride as a condensing agent as used by Backes, West and

Whiteley (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 371). The amide was extracted with benzene in which it is soluble. It was crystallised from alcohol as yellowish, glistening, feathery needles, m. p. 182°. All the three malon-nitranilides were soluble in alcohol, acetic acid, benzene and toluene; sparingly so in carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, nitrobenzene, ethyl acetate but insoluble in ether, carbon disulphide and light petroleum. [Found: N, 16.41 (*ortho*), 16.48 (*meta*), 16.13 (*para*). $C_{15}H_{12}N_4O_5$ requires N, 16.28 per cent.].

Dichloromalon-di-m-nitranilide.—Malon-di-*m*-nitranilide (1 g.) and sulphuryl chloride (1 g.) were made to react by the method followed in the preparation of dichloromalon-diphenylamide (Naik and Shah, *loc.cit.*). The product obtained was crystallised from alcohol in grey leaflets, m.p. 166°.

It is fairly soluble in alcohol, acetic acid, benzene, and toluene; fairly so in nitrobenzene, carbon tetrachloride and ethyl acetate, but almost insoluble in ether, carbon disulphide and light petroleum. (Found: Cl, 17.31. $C_{15}H_{10}O_6N_4Cl_2$ requires Cl, 17.19 per cent.).

Dichloromalon-di-p-nitranilide.—The above compound was obtained as a yellow crystalline mass when malon-di-*p*-nitranilide (1 g.) was treated with sulphuryl chloride (1 g.) in the presence of 50 c. c. of benzene in the usual way. It was crystallised from alcohol in yellowish needles, m.p. 178°. It behaves in almost the same way with different organic solvents, as the previous one does. (Found: Cl, 17.35. $C_{15}H_{10}O_6N_4Cl_2$ requires Cl, 17.19 per cent.).

Dichloromalon-di-o-nitranilide.—It was prepared from malon-di-*o*-nitranilide (1 g.) and sulphuryl chloride (1 g.) in the presence of dry benzene in the usual way. The solid product was crystallised from alcohol in yellowish prisms, m.p. 152°. The solubility of this compound is of the same order as that of the previous ones. (Found: Cl, 17.61. $C_{15}H_{10}O_6N_4Cl_2$ requires Cl, 17.19 per cent.).

Dichloromalon-diethylamide.—On treating malon-diethylamide (1 g.) with sulphuryl chloride (1 g.) in the usual way, white mass was deposited on standing. The resulting product was crystallised from alcohol in the form of white needles, m.p. 131°. The product has a solubility of the same order as that of the compound above described. (Found: Cl, 31.30. $C_7H_{12}O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 30.28 per cent.).

Dichloromalon-di-isobutylamide.—This compound was prepared from malon-di-isobutylamide (1 g.) and sulphuryl chloride (1.4 g.) in

the same way as the preceding chloride. After the reaction was over, the product crystallised from water in the form of white needles, m.p. 84°. It is soluble in almost all organic solvents except light petroleum. (Found : Cl, 25.19. $C_{12}H_{20}O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 25.09 per cent.).

Dichloromalon-diheptylamide.—Malon-diheptylamide (1 g.) and sulphuryl chloride (1 g.) were made to react in the usual way described. The mass on crystallisation from benzene gave colourless prismatic needles, m.p. 90°. It is found to be identical with the dichloromalon-diheptylamide prepared by Naik and Trivedi (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 246) by condensation of the amide with selenium tetrachloride.

Dichloromalon-di-(1 : 4 : 5) xylidide.—The above compound was obtained as a colourless crystalline mass, when malon-di-(1 : 4 : 5) xylidide (2 g.) and sulphuryl chloride (2 g.) were treated in the usual way. It was crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 170°. It is found to be identical with dichloromalon-di-(1 : 4 : 5) xylidide prepared by Naik and Trivedi (*loc. cit.*)

Dichloromalonamide.—As under the above conditions the malonamide was inactive, it was directly treated with sulphuryl chloride. The reaction started slowly on heating, with an evolution of sulphur dioxide and hydrogen chloride. When the reaction slackened after three hours, the liquid was diluted with acetic acid and filtered hot. The filtrate on standing gave colourless, shining needles. They were washed with dry petroleum and crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m. p. 203°. It is found to be identical with dichloromalonamide prepared by Zincke and Kegel (*Ber.*, 1890, 23, 245).

Monochloromalon-tetraphenylamide.—Malontetraphenylamide (1 g.) and sulphuryl chloride (0.5 g.) were made to react as usual. The filtrate on leaving overnight deposited colourless crystals, which were recrystallised from benzene, m. p. 204°. It is found to be identical with monochloromalon-tetraphenylamide prepared by West (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2200) by direct chlorination of the amide.

Preparation of Methylmalon-diethylamide.—The amide was prepared from methylmalonic ester and ethylamine by the method of Backes, West and Whitely (*loc. cit.*, p. 366) adopted for the preparation of malon-diethylamide. The mass was crystallised from benzene in colourless needles, m. p. 151°.

It is fairly soluble in almost all organic solvents and also in water, but insoluble in light petroleum. (Found : N, 16.53. $C_8H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires N, 16.28 per cent.).

Monochloromethylmalon-diethylamide.—This compound was prepared by treating methylmalon-diethylamide (1 g.) with sulphuryl chloride (1 g.) in the usual way. Colourless needles were obtained on standing for a day. It was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 108°. Its solubility in different organic solvents closely resembles that of dichloromalon-diethylamide. (Found : Cl, 17.61. $C_8H_{15}O_2N_2Cl$ requires Cl, 17.15 per cent.)

Preparation of Methylmalon-di-isobutylamide.—This amide is prepared from methylmalonic ester (10 g.) and isobutylamine (9 g.) by the method adopted by Backes, West and Whiteley (*loc. cit.*) for the preparation of malon-*n*-propylamide. The mass was removed from the tube by dissolving in benzene. This solution on concentration gave white mass, which when crystallised from alcohol gave colourless needles, m. p. 133°. Its solubility is of the same order as that of the preceding compound. (Found : N, 12.64. $C_{12}H_{24}O_2N_2$ requires N, 12.28 per cent.).

Monochloromethylmalon-di-isobutylamide.—Methylmalon-di-isobutylamide (1 g.) and sulphuryl chloride (1 g.) were made to react in the usual way. The liquid on standing overnight, gave white mass, which when crystallised from alcohol yielded colourless needles, m. p. 102°. It closely resembles the preceding compound, in its solubility. (Found : Cl, 13.79. $C_{12}H_{23}N_2O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 13.52 per cent.).

Monochloromethylmalon-dibenzylamide. — This compound was prepared from methylmalondibenzylamide (2 g.) and sulphuryl chloride (2 g.) in the usual way. The product, when crystallised from benzene, gave shining pearly plates, m. p. 159°. It is soluble in chloroform and other organic solvents, like the above enumerated compound but is insoluble in light petroleum, ether and water. (Found : Cl, 11.13. $C_{18}H_{10}O_2N_2Cl$ requires Cl, 10.74 per cent.).

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